

A Systematic mapping Review of Business Intelligence

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Abstract:

Experience in software engineering in general and Business Intelligence(BI) and analytics, in particular, involved various approaches, models, tools and criteria to select and implement the right BI system that meets the decision-maker expectations. Those multiple disciplines were appointed in the BI industry, addressed in research, and depicted thought surveys conducted by well-known advisor organizations similar to Gartner, Forrester, and others. However, to our knowledge, few systematic reviews have been conducted to identify and analyze Business Intelligence (BI) disciplines explored and cited in the literature.

This paper aims to identify and analyze BI and analytics publications according to five perspectives: publication channel, type of contribution, trends over time, domain and covered area. It performs a systematic mapping review of papers published in the period 2000–2017 and reviews them based on an automated search. This mapping study revealed that most researchers focus on proposing or analyzing models and approaches related to BI systems.

Keywords: Analytics, trends, business intelligence, Software engineering, Systematic Review.

Introduction

Which decision is the most effective? In live like in professional word, we are continually making decisions to achieve our personal, organizational or business goals. Some decisions are with a short-term impact while others process medium or long term impact. Indeed, a real challenge is to make effective decisions that are based on factual insights, with a clear goal, and the means to measure actions that contribute to achieving the objectives pursued.

In Finance, Government, Education, Healthcare and more others domains, effective decisions are expected from each organization level's, vertically from simple employee to Chief Executive Officer(CEO) and cross-domain: Human resource, finance, IT, sales, and so on. In order to assist organizations in this decision-making process, Decision Support System(DSS) was introduced since 1970 and thereafter, Business Intelligence systems have emerged in the early 90s as a solution offering appropriate data capabilities [1] [2] to provide organizations with valuable information for their decision-making process at various levels.

The purpose of this paper is to cross over BI literature and BI industry through a systematic mapping review, then, to gain insights into trends, domains, and contributions of the researcher in Business Intelligence. Since the limits and the connections between Business Intelligence and the other related fields like data analytics, big data, machine learning, ... are not clearly defined, and furthermore, to depict what topics are still considered by researchers as part of BI field or not, this study is interesting, particularly, with publications that have used the keyword "Business Intelligence explicitly" in the title.

From an industry perspective, leading research and advisory companies provides periodically important surveys and studies of trends and best practices that support organizations in their strategic decisions. Among the most active ones in the Business Intelligence field are Gartner, Forrester, and IDC, which imply a huge influence on purchasing and an unequaled events business. From a scientific research perspective, there is a lack of periodic reviews that provide this type of insights to evaluate and orient the scientific community (authors and reviewers) on searching among the most demanded topics.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. An introduction to Business Intelligence fields and the related works are addressed in section 2 and 3 respectively. An overview of the research methodology of BI publications and the conducted systematic mapping review is addressed in section 3. Section 4 presents the results. Finally, section 4 discusses the results of this systematic review before drawing conclusions and future work.

Backgrounds

Decision making can be presented as a problem of choice among several alternatives and is defined in the literature as a process of constructing the alternatives [3]. When making a decision, a person draws on existing knowledge to find

out what the current situation is and what is needed? Then creates new knowledge of what to do with resources, and what will be the future state (expected results)? Information is the raw material of this decision making process.

Time is a critical factor in the decision-making process. Even if we acquire tools that help to take a decision if these tools can not inform decision makers at the right time about the way to take an action a disaster can occur.

In current challenging context with Time pressure on the decision maker, insufficient or too much information, accuracy versus speed, and effectiveness versus efficiency, having a decision support system (DSS) that supports people who make decisions is crucial. This paper focuses on a specific class of DSSs which is Business Intelligence.

Business Intelligence creates from internal and external organization data, the information and the knowledge that help members, the executives and the operational ones, in their decision making process.

Literature proposes various definitions of Business Intelligence with the same finality which aims to enhance organization performance and decision-making process by reducing wasting costs and time [4] and allowing a continuous improvement of profit and performance (Williams and Williams (2007)). The paper [5] considers BI as a philosophy of strategies, processes, applications, data, products, technologies and technical architectures that support the collection, analysis, presentation, and dissemination of business information. In a business context, the ability of learning and understanding business is an important factor added in the Gartner definition which allows achieving higher business goals.

In the last decades, Business Intelligence gets an important place in every organization with strong high level sponsorship, not only for business companies but also for social services organizations (healthcare, education,...), government, industry, and others. Despite the fact that business intelligence projects are IT projects which must ensure a neutral cross-domain approach in every organization, Business Intelligence requires both: (1) mixed competencies of Information Technology (IT) and business skills and (2) a maturity in IT/functional relationship.

BI is a data-driven process that combines data storage and gathering with knowledge management to provide improve the decision making process [6]. In addition to today BI' challenges, the phenomenon of big data that comes describing larger, volatile and complex data sets and amplifies BI challenges which cannot be addressed using traditional BI methodologies. With the emergence of big data, the meaning and scope of analytics have evolved also. Predictive and prescriptive analytics took an important place in addition to visual analytics of descriptive data, that's still the prominent form of analytics.

: Maturity levels by Gartner [7]

A governance dimension of the BI program that manages people, skills, processes, metrics and other components, as well as technologies, provides organizations the wider insight they need to make good decisions. This dimension cannot be set up at one shot; it takes time to be built with the right BI technologies and associated skills. From a

governance perspective, Gartner [7] proposes to evaluate the BI maturity level in the organization following 5 levels as illustrated in fig. 1.

From the unaware level where information still in a spreadsheet and ad-hoc report with no formal process, tool or practices and no BI responsible or sponsor which produces a little to no trust on this BI status. In the second maturity level "Opportunistic," each project searches to optimize process through its own BI assets with limited users, inconsistent data and no optimized cost. In the third level "Standards" people, processes and technologies start to transverse across multiple business units but still not linked to enterprise goals. The "Enterprise" level involves that the COE (for example) become the program sponsors, which allows establishing a BI strategy that guides the enterprise strategy. The last level of Gartner's maturity model is "Transformative" which focuses on the business value and not only on internal processes.

Related work

In the literature review [8], the author proposes an empirical study I BI and gives a focus on which parts of the BI business value framework have attracted researchers' attention and what opportunities these offer for future research. To improve organizational performance, the author proposes a theoretical framework based on five themes which are the environmental factors, BI conversion process, BI use process, BI competitive process and latency effects [8].

M. Gibson and al. [9] have proposed a literature review to point the intangible benefits of Business Intelligence and depicted the complexity to calculate the benefits of a decision support system in general and BI in particular for an organization using traditional evaluation techniques. The BI benefits can be evaluated in operational level and tactical level, however, it is difficult to assess them in strategic level. Starting from IT business value point of view, the [10] paper has depicted the business value of BI using a dual approach that integrates insights gained from general IT and specific BI research. From 34 reviewed papers in [10] which examined the business value of BI, the data warehouse (DW), or business analytics the author find that the distinction between operational and strategic BI capabilities is crucial to understanding BI value creation.

In decision support system, knowing the type of decision, strategic or operational, is mandatory, however, focus on the type of user that makes the decision is also fundamental [11] in order to identify what are the patterns of BI use in organizations. Use patterns in decision support are normally concerned with the type of decision to be supported and the type of manager that makes the decision. The reason for this focus is that the type of task and type of user in DSS are fundamentally different from the users and tasks supported by enterprise transaction-based, web-based, mobile, social systems, and other information systems.

Others literature reviews were interested in current BI research trends and future direction of business intelligence in regard with industries. From a banking perspective, The paper [12] presents an automated text mining literature analysis that concerns the period 2002 to 2013 ad focused on BI applications within the banking industry.

Research methodology

A systematic literature review is a methodology to identify, evaluate and interpret all available research relevant to a specific research problem [13]. Despite the fact that a SLRs require considerably more effort than traditional literature reviews, they allow mainly (with a well-defined methodology) to make less biased results, to provide information about the effects of some phenomenon across a wide range of settings and empirical methods [14]. A systematic mapping is a particular type of an SLR that allows the evidence in a domain to be plotted at a high level of granularity and provides a wide overview of a research area with less highly focused search terms.

: The Systematic mapping review process

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This paper proposes a systematic mapping review(SMR) of Business intelligence field which involves several discrete activities. The SMR consists of three stages and five activities as illustrated in Fig. 2 that shows the SMR process and presents each stage included:

in stage 1 « planning the review », SMR starts with the “problem definition” activity through a list of research questions, then « search strategies » activity which defines literature search terms, sources, and selection criteria,

stage 2 of this SMR is « conducting the review » that includes the « papers classification » activity, which involves the data extraction to classify selected papers based on predefined dimensions thereafter « data analysis »,

and finally stage 3 « reporting ».

Research questions

The overall objective of our study is to gain insight into the business area, research contribution, trends over time and publication channel of BI papers from literature perspective. In order to obtain a detailed view of this topic, this systematic mapping study addresses five research questions (RQ).

: Research Questions for Systematic Map

No.	Research question	Main motivation
RQ1	Which publication channels are the main targets for BI researcher?	To identify where BI research can be found as well as the good targets for publication of future studies
RQ2	How has the frequency of BI publications changed over time?	To identify BI publication trends over time
RQ3	What are the publication types and the contribution in BI ?	To explore the different types of research reported in BI literature
RQ4	In which domain of BI, publications were interested?	This question allows us to identify which business area or domain that involves BI researchers and business investment
RQ5	Which publishers are the most evolved over time?	To know which publishers are more interested in the BI field

Table I presents the five RQs with their corresponding motivations. These questions allowed us to focus this study in the BI field and to provide business intelligence researchers and practitioners an overview, from a literature point of view.

Search strategy

To capture relevant BI papers that answer these research questions, the “Search strategy” phase involves three steps. The first step of “Search strategy” defines the key search terms and strings. The second step of “Search strategy” applies these search strings on a set of selected digital libraries to extract all the relevant papers. Then, the third step designs a search procedure to ensure that no relevant paper had been left out. These three steps are described in detail below.

: search terms and queries

No.	Search terms	Search Query
Query 1	classification, selection	classification OR analysis OR categorization OR sorting OR taxonomy OR selection OR choice OR option OR preference
Query 2	factors, grouping	grouping OR aggregation OR association OR cluster OR collection OR gathering OR organization OR set OR factors OR aspect OR consideration OR element OR item OR detail OR entry OR matter OR particular OR note OR notice
Query 3	component	feature OR attribute OR facet OR point OR property OR quality OR characteristic OR specific OR component OR part OR piece OR unit
Query 4	benchmark, criteria	criteria OR "benchmark" OR measure OR norm OR par OR principle OR proof OR rule OR standard OR benchmark OR criterion OR example OR gauge OR level OR reference
Query 5	requirements	requirements OR demand OR essential OR necessity OR need OR precondition OR prerequisite OR qualification OR requisite OR specification OR stipulation OR
Query 6	capabilities	capabilities OR ability OR capacity OR competence OR facility OR faculty OR means OR potential OR potentiality OR power OR proficiency OR wherewithal
Query 7	evaluation	evaluation OR appraisal OR assessment OR calculation OR estimate OR estimation OR judgment OR opinion OR rating OR valuation
Query 8	review	review OR assess OR criticize OR discuss OR evaluate OR examine OR inspect OR judge OR "read through" OR scrutinize OR study OR weigh OR retrospect OR revision OR look
Query 9	framework	techniques OR approach OR method OR mode OR technology OR framework OR core OR foundation OR frame OR " frame of reference" OR schema OR structure OR " the bare bones."
Query 10	system	application OR pertinence OR purpose OR relevance OR use OR value OR appeal OR claim OR inquiry OR request OR requisition OR solicitation OR system OR software OR application OR tool

Search terms

We derived the search terms using the following series of tasks:

Identify the main terms are providing the maximum coverage of the review questions listed in table 2.

Search for the synonyms and spelling variations of the main terms.

Use the Boolean operator OR to join synonymous terms, in order to retrieve any record containing either (or all) of the terms.

Use the Boolean operator AND to connect the main term “Business Intelligence,” in order to retrieve any record containing all the terms.

The complete set of search terms was formulated in 10 queries as illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** II.

Literature resources

To extract the relevant publications, we performed an automated search using Harzing's Publish or **Perish tool** [15], which assists researchers to retrieve publications and to analyze academic citations. Perish uses a variety of data sources (including Google Scholar and Microsoft Academic Search) to obtain the raw citations, then analyzes them and presents interesting metrics : Total number of papers and total number of citations, Average citations per paper, citations per author, papers per author, and citations per year, and other metrics.

This work uses the electronic databases “Google scholar,” which index millions of papers from diverse types of publication channels such as journals, conferences, workshops, and so on, and they have been used as sources for previous systematic literature reviews related to computer science.

The reference lists of all relevant papers were stored and organized using a free bibliographic tool named Zotero. Zotero assists in detecting duplicate papers, renames the bibliographies properly, stores papers automatically and generates bibliography scripts. It also simplifies the navigation in papers through various search options.

Study selection

Each of the selected papers identified in the initial search stage was evaluated automatically using the inclusion and exclusion criteria, to determine whether it should be retained or rejected.

Inclusion criteria:

IC1 : include all publication types, except the citations and blog posts

IC2: include publications that have a clear bibliography: title, year, authors, publisher or source.

Exclusion criteria:

EC1: Duplicate publications of the same study (where several publications of the same study exist, only the most complete one is included in the review). Duplication rule is based on the title and authors strings.

EC2 : not English papers

EC3: papers published earlier than 2000 and later than 2017.

EC4: Publications that concern one of the areas: Artificial intelligence, Collective intelligence, cultural intelligence, economic intelligence, emotional intelligence with an automatic elimination based on title text analysis

EC5 : publications that have in the title the phrase “Emotional Intelligence,” “Cultural intelligence” and “Collective intelligence.”

Quality assessment

Data extraction strategy and synthesis

A data extraction form was created and completed for each of the selected papers to address the research questions of this systematic mapping review.

: data extraction form

Attribute	Description	Mandatory
Data extractor	Automatic (Perish)	

Id	Incremental numerical identifier given to each publication	*
Q	The identifier of the Query used in the search query	*
Title	Title of the paper	*
Year	Publication year of the publication	*
Authors	Names of authors	*
Channel	Publication source name or channel	*
Publisher	The publisher of the publication	
Article URL	The publication URL	
Type	Type of publication if exists: book, paper...	
Goal	publication approach or type of contribution	x
Area	The publication domain or area	x
Criteria	Cited business Intelligence criteria/components/feature and importance degree	x

The main data extracted for each publication are listed in table III then analyzed from 5 question-oriented perspectives.

RQ1: This requires that all publication sources are identified. 2 types of data are analyzed: publication channel and publisher name. Publishers those having more than 8 publications were identified and listed.

The extracted publication channels are similar to: 'Journal,' 'Conference,' 'Workshop,' and so on

Publisher name : includes the name or the abbreviation of the publisher

RQ2: this question has a need of the publication year's information.

RQ3: this question requires that for each publication, the research contribution is identified. The main keywords used in this study to capture each publication contribution are (respectively): reviews and surveys Proposal and model analysis, Comparatives and evaluations, Solution; System or technology study, case study and applications.

RQ4: this question requires that for each publication, the BI domain is identified.

The keywords used to identify which business domain is concerned by the publications are Geospatial, Healthcare, Agriculture, Electrical, Finance, Education, Finance and bank, supply chain, tourism and location, public services and sales and marketing.

The keywords used to identify some generic domains that were studied are competitive analysis, social and sentiment analysis, web and SEO, Security, Cloud, others IT and decision making.

RQ5: this question involves that the publication areas are clear and identified. Table IV presents keywords used to classify publication areas.

keywords used to identify publication areas

Area	Keywords of the area
Business intelligence	Data warehouse, Datawarehouse, Decision, Bigdata, Big data, Visual Analytics, Data mining, Data mining, Business intelligence, Business-intelligence
Artificial intelligence	Artificial intelligence
Emotional intelligence	Emotional intelligence
Competitive intelligence	Competitive intelligence
Market intelligence	Market intelligence
Economic intelligence	Economic intelligence
Collective intelligence	Collective intelligence
Cultural intelligence	Cultural
Business process	Business process

To allow an efficient and automated analysis of extracted data (cf. III), a data model is proposed in this study, which allows illustrating BI publications using the entity-relation model. This entity-relation model includes one denormalized table that includes the extracted data. The other tables present the analysis's axis that was selected to analyze the SMR results.

Threats to validity

The main threats to the validity of this review are analyzed in the following three respects:

Study selection bias : We should mention that the papers presented in this study are extracted on the basis of titles, a few abstract was examined in order to validate publication source and context.

Publication year was corrected for 6 publications on the basis of citations(Enhancing Business-Intelligence Tools with Value-Driven Recommendations)

>2016 : R Amici, F Oboni, C Oboni Linking, « a Business Intelligence Geotechnical platform to a responsive Risk Evaluation platform »

>2010 : YK Lin, « Clinical Decision Support as a Business Intelligence Application »

>2012 : SM Aboelnaga, RM Husseinand, HM Abdalkader, « Classification in Business Intelligence using Variable Consistency Dominance-based Rough Set Approach »

>2014 : C Sellitto, “Business Intelligence Project Implementation: A Retail Company Case Study in C-and-A »

>2014 : W POONNAWAT, P LEHMANN, “A Framework of using DSS in Business Simulation Games Study Object: Business Intelligence and Corporate Performance Management »

Data extraction bias : data extraction process was automatically using a tool. However, one actor was involved in data cleaning operation to fill incomplete data (year, publisher, channel)

Results and discussion

This section presents our findings on the basis of extracted publications using the mapping review described above. We used a data visualization tool to evaluate and analyze the findings of the collected publications. Firstly, we

introduce an overview of the result of the selection process; and secondly, all the results for each research question are reported.

: number of publications per query

Query	Number of publications
Q10	980
Q9	980
Q8	638
Q1	508
Q2	363
Q3	270
Q7	210
Q6	199
Q4	166
Q5	145
Total	4459

Overview of the selected studies

4459 publications were identified automatically from the google scholar library using the 10 queries presented above. Table 5 presents the number of publications that was founded per query. The 2 inclusion criteria IC1 and IC2 were applied in the first time and given 2948 publications in the result.

: The Systematic mapping review process

After applying the exclusion criteria EC1, 654 duplicates among the 4459 were eliminated based on title and authors' data as shown in fig. 3.

Then Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied respectively: EC2, EC3, and EC4 and were allowed to extract relevant publications (2167) as described in fig. 3. In the next sections, 2167 publications data are analyzed and discussed from the 5 research questions perspectives.

RQ1 : Which publication channels are the main targets for BI research?

Various publication channels were explored by BI researchers. Journals and reviews are at the top of publication channels with more 43%. This rate can be considered a normal rate since researchers tend to prefer journal publications rather than conferences [16].

: Classification of publications by channel

: publication channels over years

Fig. 4 and Fig.5 illustrates our finding using a bar chart. This study shows that 17% of the publications are from the Academic and university publishers which include a thesis and advanced work concertation's. In the third place, Conferences make 15%, approximately, because conferences have the advantages of bringing researchers together by offering the opportunity to present and discuss the paper with peers [17]. The trends in the publication are increasing over the years, especially for reviews and journals with a noticeable peak level in 2012(443 publications).

RQ2: How has the frequency of BI publications changed over time?

The trends of BI publications have known 3 peaks at 2008, 2012 and 2016 respectively. In general terms, the last decade has noted a significant increase in the number of publications, that can be explained by the appearance of new data sources such as unstructured online data (clickstreams, social network data,). From an industry perspective, and on the basis of Gartner report, which is the most exhaustive in comparison with Forrester and Wisdom, Gartner report considers various Business Intelligence capability areas that were awaited by industry, including, Data discovery and exploration, Data Management and Governance, and so on. In parallel, Research in the field of BI was evolving and trying to find solutions to those industrial areas.

: trends in the number of publications

As shown in Fig. 5. **Error! Reference source not found.** and confirmed in Fig. 6. **Error! Reference source not found.**, the volume of publications increases over time with a major peak registered in the year 2012. Fig. 6. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows that journal and review channel is the first concerned with this 2012 peak (green line).

RQ3 :What are the main research contributions ?

: classification of publication according to contribution type

Proposal and model analysis constitutes 30% of total publications with 601 publications as illustrated in Fig. 7. The latter proposes or develops business intelligence proposals that may concern process, method, tools, approach, the solution to support the organizational needs in terms of decision support. 7% of publications propose a BI comparative and evaluation studies of existing proposals, including solutions, methods and frameworks and only 6% provide case studies.

This result shows that the number of case-study contributions remains low in comparison with the other research contributions. The case study is a research strategy which provides knowledge and focuses on understanding the dynamics present within a single case and can be used to accomplish various aims: to provide a description, test theory, or generate theory. The most important interest here is in this last aim, theory generation from case study evidence [18].

RQ4 : in which domains, BI publications were interested ?

: classification of publications by domains (Business and Generic)

Data exploration of this Systematic Mapping Review result depicts two types of domains: business domains(industries) and generic domains(which include some specific software engineering fields) as illustrated in Fig. 8. Financial services and investment banking are in the top of industries list involved by a researcher with 13%. Thereafter, we found education with 12%, Healthcare with 10% and sales ad marketing research with 9%.

: classification of publications by domains (Business and Generic)

Fig. 9. Illustrates the trends over a year of publications related to business domains and publications related to generic domains. The business domain includes industry oriented publications, examples : banking, health, tourism,. Generic domain concerns software disciplines in relation with BI, examples : decision making, cloud,competitive analysis, his study indicates that, since 2008, business domains publications become more important than generic domain and evolve in this way : in 2014, more than 73% of publications are related to business domain, more than 25% among the 73% is for Finance and banking sub domain.

RQ5 : Which publishers are the most involved overtime?

Publisher	% of Total publicati..	Number of Records
IEEE	21.95%	758,0
Springer	13.93%	481,0
Google Patents	13.87%	479,0
search.proquest.com	9.73%	336,0
Elsevier	7.88%	272,0
researchgate.net	6.98%	241,0
aisel.aisnet.org	6.86%	237,0
books.google.com	6.55%	226,0
Others	6.20%	214,0
en.cnki.com.cn	6.05%	209,0

: top 10 publishers

IEEE is positioned in the first among the most involved publishers of BI research with 22% as illustrated in Fig. 9. Spring and Google Patents are in the second position with 14%.

Additionally, This paper has adopted text mining(TM) approach to analyze and extract information from each “publication title” considered in this literature analysis. The adopted TM approach includes several common steps over the corpus of documents, for stripping extra white spaces, removing numbers, punctuation and English stop words, converting all words in lower case, reducing the terms of the dictionary to a common term, and finally defining the document term matrix. This last is a bi-dimensional representation used as an input for the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (the dimensions are the articles and the terms, and each cell contains the frequency of the term in the article).

- viii. V. Trieu, "Getting value from Business Intelligence systems: A review and research agenda," *Decision Support Systems*, 2017.
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